

Shared spaces: transport networks to link ecological communities in the UK – a regional perspective

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Summary

Local Nature Recovery Strategies (LNRS) are instrumental in delivering landscape-wide nature recovery and can facilitate a co-ordinated approach to habitat connectivity across key stakeholders. This paper presents a process tool developed in the R “markdown” which can assist in stakeholder consultation leading to concrete initiatives for habitat management, restoration and creation. The process maps connectivity hotspots close to the transportation network to identify locations where the verge can assist in habitat connectivity and locations of wildlife-vehicle-collisions (WVC) risk. The process is demonstrated using a case study of woodland habitat in the West Midlands.

KEYWORDS: Biodiversity Net Gain, habitat connectivity, transportation infrastructure verges, geospatial analysis, R programming

1. Introduction

This paper presents a scalable, “proof in principle” tool, which can be utilised in discussions between Transport Providers and Local Authorities to incorporate linear transportation verges into regional and ultimately landscape-scale nature recovery objectives, including discussions as part of a Local Nature Recovery Strategy (LNRS). It utilises a case study of broadleaf woodland in the West Midlands Combined Authority (WMCA) region, UK.

Fifteen years ago, the Lawton Review emphasised that large scale habitat improvement and restored ecological processes can only be realised through coordinated action at the local scale and across the spectrum of stakeholders. The challenge was encapsulated with the words “more, bigger, better, and joined”. Fragments of good condition semi-natural habitat are required to connect populations, with natural and man-made linear features (managed proactively by public bodies and other authorities) functioning as corridors for movement and dispersal (Lawton, 2010). Shortly after this, the UK Biodiversity Action plan listed 65 habitats for prioritised conservation action (BRIG, 2011).

In 2018 the UK’s 25 Year Environment plan formulated the principles for the Nature Recovery Network to connect priority habitats (DEFRA, 2018). In the same year, the Varley Report called on action from the UK rail network to commit to “a railway for people and wildlife” (Varley, 2018), and Network Rail responded with its Biodiversity Action Plan, which acknowledges the huge potential for verge vegetation to assist in habitat connectivity (Network Rail, 2020). The Nature Networks Evidence handbook was also released in 2020 to provide practical tools to design nature networks (Crick, 2020). At the local level, guidance for Nature Recovery Strategies was released, and functions to strengthen the biodiversity duty on public authorities, wherein stakeholders agree key priorities and actions and

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map where they will take place, with connectivity as a key consideration. (DEFRA, 2023).

However, there is no doubt that verge vegetation can present challenges to rail and road operations, especially with the increased frequency of extreme weather events across the globe (Greenham et al., 2024b). Additionally, wildlife-vehicle collisions (WVCs) are an indicator of the need for wildlife to traverse transportation networks (Grilo et al., 2011, Gardiner et al., 2018), and the negative consequences for wildlife if safe routes are not provided. Nevertheless, literature reviews show that verge vegetation can function as both habitat and dispersal routes for many life-forms (Cork et al., 2024).

Against this background, the quality and availability of UK-specific spatial datasets has increased dramatically, with free issue LiDAR derived products at resolutions below 1m (EA, 2022, EA, 2024) and satellite datasets from 10m resolution (Copernicus, from 2015). Species occurrence datasets are centrally coordinated and freely available through the Global Biodiversity Information Facility, among others (GBIF, 2023). Many data analysis packages and functions are mature, well maintained and readily available within GIS software and Python/ R environments (CRAN, 2024-10-31).

These data and tools provide the raw materials for a methodology to identify connectivity “hotspots” along the rail network (and similarly for the road network), and to prioritise locations for conservation and restoration of verge vegetation as well as wildlife crossing arrangements. This will help transport professionals to provide meaningful regional contributions towards nature recovery whilst minimising disruption and cost to rail (and road) operations.

2. Methodological Approach

An important aspect of the scoping process is to understand region-specific priorities for species and habitat recovery. This case study focuses on the West Midlands Combined Authority (WMCA) region, and the University of Birmingham are part of the Species, Habitats and Protected Sites working group for the WMCA LNRS. This builds on previous spatial work with WMCA on Climate Risk and Vulnerability mapping (Greenham et al., 2024a).

Priority Habitats are those of principal importance for the purpose of conserving biodiversity (BRIG, 2011). WMCA is currently in the process of developing LNRS short-lists of species and habitats. In the meantime, deciduous woodland is identified in Natural England’s Priority Habitat Inventory (Natural England, 2024), with ongoing tree-planting objectives likely to benefit from outputs. WMCA is a heavily human-altered region with a high degree of fragmentation of existing core habitats, and previous research indicates that in such heavily urbanised areas, verges can provide a significant contribution to ecological connectivity (Cork et al., 2024). This study therefore hypothesises that the woody vegetation along transportation verges will be a productive case-study in lieu of our LNRS short lists.

This methodology has been applied to the deciduous woodland dataset (Natural England, 2024) and represents core habitat locations for woodland species assemblages. The Vegetation Object Model (VOM) maps vegetation objects above 2.5 metres height and has been used to map potential connectivity routes between core habitats (EA, 2024). For the railway, this study utilised “NWR Reference lines” for idealised Engineer’s Line Reference (ELR) centrelines (Network Rail, 2025).

The workflow is captured in a series of R Markdown documents which are integrated into the R Studio Integrated Development Environment (IDE), and step through each process stage in a user-friendly webpage format, displaying interactive map outputs. R packages and libraries are utilised (CRAN, 2024-10-31), with links out to Java and Julia environments where necessary to integrate with other packages.

The omniscap and circuitscape packages (Landau, 2021, Edelman, 2020) , which utilise circuit

theory to model habitat connectivity in heterogeneous landscapes, have been selected due to their common usage amongst researchers (Dutta et al., 2022) (Dutta et al., 2022) as well as their recent integration into a Julia environment with attendant processing speed improvements. The “conductance surface” is a 10m resolution raster of percentage tree cover. For species-level connectivity models, conductance will be in the form of habitat suitability maps, generated using GBIF occurrence data and the maxent (dismo) and maxnet R packages. These packages use the principles of maximum entropy to determine likelihood of occurrence based on a set of environmental variables (Phillips et al., 2004). Omniscape outputs are expressed as cumulative current (representing total connectivity) and normalised current (representing channelised flow due to obstructions to flow) which are a good indicator of verge connectivity in a built-up area.

Figure 1 WMCA - percent tree cover at 50m resolution (derived from VOM)

Figure 2 WMCA - normalised current representing channelised flow (using omniscap)

The sensitivity of input variables is being tested, varying radius (a proxy for dispersal distance), conductance surface resolution and whether core habitat is the sole source, or whether tree cover values over a specified threshold can represent core habitat.

Each ELR was divided into 10m sections with left and right buffers of 100m width on either side of the route to capture connectivity statistics. R code was used to determine locations with high “crossing potential” and “high longitudinal connectivity” where rail verges are likely to be successful for dispersal. Network Rail “Waymarks” have been added to allow ready pinpointing of hotspot locations in NR’s standardised ELR measurement system.

Figure 3 100m wide by 10m long rail segments to capture connectivity statistics

By referencing connectivity statistics into tree polygons from the National Tree Map (NTM) (Bluesky Ltd, 2024) and clipping to rail and road land ownership boundaries, transport providers can manage an asset database of trees with metadata containing connectivity statistics, habitat suitability and tree fall risk (based on height and proximity to track).

3. Preliminary results and future objectives

R markdown files were created for the complete process described above and have the flexibility to produce additional outputs by using revised or alternative datasets and variable combinations. Future iterations will bring in blended habitat suitability data for species assemblages when shortlists are available from the WMCA LNRS. Also, sensitivity analysis will be carried out to determine the feasibility of blended connectivity scores for different variable combinations. It is hoped that these outputs can be incorporated into future development of Nature Recovery proposals by WMCA.

Figure 4 Magnified views showing hotspots for verge connectivity length (left) and WVC risk (right)

Outputs will have the potential to facilitate meaningful stakeholder engagement of LNRS objectives between WMCA and Network Rail. Thereafter, providing Network Rail with a resource to locate and manage verge vegetation assets for ecological connectivity along the rail corridor as well as understanding areas of high WVC risk across the West Midlands.

Figure 5 Tree crown polygons with connectivity statistics (utilising NTM, Bluesky Ltd)

Future improvement of this approach will consider the effects of climate change on habitat suitability, and associated changes in connectivity patterns. This information can provide valuable insights into the robustness of local nature recovery proposals.

4. Conclusions

This study's approach introduces a decision support tool for transport providers and local authorities towards the shared goal of nature recovery. The outputs will help transport providers to maximise the value of verge vegetation protection and restoration efforts whilst minimising expenditure and reducing the risk of wildlife-vehicle collisions. Stakeholder engagement in the production of outputs can increase understanding of issues, increase ownership and adoption, leading to positive outcomes.

The tool can help to present the importance of rail verge vegetation for nature recovery within the

WMCA region, thereby opening lines of communication. The model can be extended to other regions and associated LNRSs to achieve landscape scale coordination. In principle and subject to data availability, the process can be applied globally within highly fragmented landscapes with a high potential for restoration and protection of rail/ road verge vegetation.

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7. Biographies

Nick Cork is a PhD researcher of Civil Engineering at the University of Birmingham, focusing on the optimisation of transport networks for habitat connectivity and biodiversity. He has also worked with WMCA and TfWM to develop a Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment (CRVA) mapping tool for the West Midlands' transport network. Prior to starting his PhD, his background was in Engineering Project Management for the UK transportation sector.

Dr Emma Ferranti is an Associate Professor in the School of Engineering at the University of Birmingham, undertaking interdisciplinary research at the intersection of infrastructure, the built environment and green infrastructure. She leads and contributes to a range of projects in the fields of transport, infrastructure resilience, climate adaptation, air quality, and green infrastructure.

Dr Rachel Fisher is an Associate Professor in the School of Engineering at the University of Birmingham, working at the interface between academia and industry. Their research focuses on extreme weather hazards, transport infrastructure resilience and climate change adaptation.

Dr Sarah Greenham is a Research Fellow in the School of Engineering at the University of Birmingham, whose research focuses on adapting cities and infrastructure to the impacts of climate change. She completed her PhD in Civil Engineering in 2023, collaborating with Transport for London on quantifying the impacts of heat and climate change on London Underground infrastructure.

Dr Elspeth Sage is an ecologist and natural capital officer at the West Midlands Combined Authority (WMCA), working on developing the Local Nature Recovery Strategy. This strategy brings together multiple partners across the region to work towards spatially planning actions for nature across the region, making our habitats bigger, better and more joined up, in support of nature recovery.

Dr Neil Strong is Biodiversity Strategy Manager at Network Rail providing expertise and support on sustainable management of the lineside necessary to improve the safety and biodiversity of the rail network.

Prof Andrew Quinn is Professor of Climate Adaptation and Director of Education in the College of Engineering and Physical Sciences at the University of Birmingham. His research focuses on the interactions between infrastructure, particularly rail and transport systems, renewable energy and extreme weather events/climate change and how these impact on the resilience of communities and services.